

**PREVENTION OF UROLITHIASIS.
(literature review)**

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Abstract

The gender presents statistics of scientific articles on the prevention of nephrological diseases with a drug containing goldenrod, mistress and rosemary. A positive effect in the prevention of urolithiasis was found.

The aim of the study. Compare the preventive effect of the drug with herbal composition (goldenrod, mistress, rosemary) in various nephrological diseases.

Research results. During the first 10 days of hospitalization of patients in the combined group, higher rates of spontaneous removal of kidney stones were noted (72.7 % against 33.3 %), stones of the upper ureter (71.4 % against 37.5 %), middle ureter (66.6 % against 33.3 %). 40%), as well as the lower stones of the ureter (90%vs. 55.5%). After 10 days of treatment, the initial leukocyturia decreased from 64.4% to 6.9% in the study group, but increased from 44.1% to 53.4% in the control group. Stones that did not disappear with the help of drug therapy were treated with extracorporeal shock wave lithotripsy, ureteroscopy with stone extraction or the installation of ureter stent, respectively. A month after the discontinuation, there was a marked increase in the average daily volume of urine in the study group compared to the control group.

The conclusion established a positive effect in patients with urolithiasis and after removal of stones. The use of a long course of treatment of patients with uncomplicated idiopathic calcium urolithiasis can reduce the risk of relapse of urolithiasis, as evidenced by a decrease in the ionic activity index and the frequency of crystalluria.

Keywords: Treatment, properties, action, kidneys, gastrology.

Actuality of theme. Therapeutic properties of goldenrod, rosemary and root of the mistress are caused by the entrances of essential oils, phenolcarboxylic acids, phthalides, bitterness, organic acids, vitamins; Currently, anti-inflammatory properties are caused mainly by the antagonism of rosemary acid with inflammatory mediators, lock of leukotriene synthesis. The combination of these plants increases the secretion of uric acid and promotes the maintenance of urine pH in the range of 6.2 - 6.8, which is important for urate and calcium - oxylate urolithiasis. Flavonoids and rosemalic acid can bind calcium and magnesium to chelate complexes with subsequent removal of them. The antispasmodic and diuretic action of the drug contributes to the self-release of small concretions and the rehabilitation of the urinary tract. A number of authors recommends applying

The main active substances are xanthenes of 1,6,8-trihydroxy-3,5,7-trimethoxyxanton, 1,8-dihydroxy-3,5,6,7-tetramethoxyxanton; Monteterapene glycosides of Geniopikrin, Genzopicroside, Sversiamarin, Amarogencin; essential oils; flavonoids: luteolin, apigenin, scutularine; phenolic acids (P-kumarova, hydroxyphenyloz, Ferulov, protocatechova); coumarins (5-formil-2,3-dihydroisocoumarin); fatty acids; nicotinamide; Monoterapene alkaloids Gencyanine, Hencyamin, Gencyanidine.

The rosemary letter found:

- alkaloids (rosemalycin),
- Ursol and rosemalic acids,
- tannins,

- essential (rosemary) oil.
- The essential oil includes α -Pinen (30 %),
- CAMPFEN (20 %),
- Cineol (24-40 %),
- Borneol (10-17%),
- L-camphor,
- Cariophilene (8%),
- Bronilacetate (2%),
- flavonoids (apigenin, luteolin),
- coffee acid,
- chlorogenic acid,
- Amirin,
- Ursulic acid,
- oleanic acid,
- Lemon, resin and bitterness.

The main active substances of the mistress are:

- Furocoumarini (Bergapten, Psoralen),
- Lecithin,
- starch,
- “Spots,
- gum,
- malic and angelic acids,
- mineral salts,
- tannins.

The composition of the substance in the goldenrod, rosemary and mistresses have anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, choleric, wound healing, hemostatic, hepatoprotective, weak laxative, antispasmodic, analgesic wound healing, hemorrhage, hepatohepatic, hepatoprotective.

This combination can be used:

- with peptic ulcer of the stomach and duodenum,
- flatulence,
- constipation,
- inflammatory diseases of the urinary tract,
- inflammatory diseases of the liver and bile ducts,
- bronchitis and pneumonia,
- diseases of the nervous system.
- with purulent wounds,
- diabetic periodontal disease, ulcers, bedsores.
- nervous exhaustion, fatigue, anorexia,
- anemia,
- migraines,
- skin diseases.

The aim of the study. Compare the preventive effect of the drug with herbal composition (goldenrod, mistress, rosemary) in various nephrological diseases.

Research results. In five studies, patients with urolithiasis received a combination of herbs as additional therapy [3, 6, 7, 8, 9]. In the observational uncontrolled study of Shapligin and Monakov [10], a decrease in bacteriuria and leukocyturia in 47 patients

who received treatment for 4 weeks and observed within 6 months was noted.

In Chernenko's publications and others. In total, 110 patients with urolithiasis were treated for 8 weeks, and 24 patients were monitored. [13,14] Both publications participated in the same patients, although patient grouping was somewhat different. It is unclear whether the control group was historical or randomized, so the statistical assessment should be interpreted with caution. However, the authors noticed a significant ($p < 0.05$) increase in 24-hour diuresis, an increase in urine pH and a decrease in uric acid in the urine. All of these parameters can be considered favorable for met prophylaxis of urate-calcium-oxalate disease. The recurrence rate in the study group was also lower than in the control group. Treatment with a herbal remedy was considered safe and was well tolerated in all 157 cases.

In a randomized, open, one-center cohort study, published CEBAN, 237 patients with urea stones up to 0.7 cm in diameter and without lesions) and without ($n = 102$) medicinal herbs (see Tab. 1) [1, 4, 5, 11, 12, 15].

Table 1.

The effect of prednisolone therapy, trinephron and their combination on the main immunological markers of autoimmune kidney pathology ($n = 8$ in each group)

Group	Research parameters			
	CD3+, $\times 10^9 / \mu$	CD4 + CD3+, %	CD8 + CD3+, %	Immunoregulatory index (CD4+/CD8+)
ПЗО	$6,7 \pm 0,15$	$65,2 \pm 0,9$	$54,1 \pm 1,15$	$2,26 \pm 0,04$
AIG	$6,5 \pm 0,11$	$61,0 \pm 1,6^*$	$35,6 \pm 1,5^*$	$3,01 \pm 0,07^*$
AIG + Prednisolone	$5,9 \pm 0,11^* / \dagger$	$62,1 \pm 1,1$	$40,2 \pm 1,5^* / \dagger$	$2,74 \pm 0,07^* / \dagger$
AIG + CAN	$6,6 \pm 0,11\#$	$61,9 \pm 1,2$	$36,2 \pm 1,6^*$	$3,00 \pm 0,09^*$
AIG + Prednisolone + CAN	$6,1 \pm 0,11^* / \dagger$	$64,2 \pm 0,7$	$44,5 \pm 0,7^* / \dagger / \#$	$2,58 \pm 0,04^* / \dagger$

* -witness reliable relative to the PZO group, $p \leq 0.05$

† - distinct reliable relative to the AII group, $p \leq 0.05$

-distinctions are probable relative to the group of prednisolone, $p \leq 0.05$

During the first 10 days of hospitalization of patients in the combined group, higher rates of spontaneous removal of kidney stones were noted (72.7 % against 33.3 %), stones of the upper ureter (71.4 % against 37.5 %), middle ureter (66.6 % against 33.3 %). 40%), as well as the lower stones of the ureter (90%vs. 55.5%). After 10 days of treatment, the initial leukocyturia decreased from 64.4% to 6.9% in the study group, but increased from 44.1% to 53.4% in the control group. Stones that did not disappear with the help of drug therapy were treated with extracorporeal shock wave lithotripsy, ureteroscopy with stone extraction or the installation of ureter stent, respectively. A month after the discontinuation, there was a marked increase in the average daily volume of urine in the study group compared to the control group. The average pH of urine increased from 5.6 to 6. 4 in the study group and re-

mained almost stable in the control (5.7-5.8). Phyto-combination treatment is considered safe and is well tolerated in all cases [16, 17].

In the observational study of Gaibullaev and Kariyev 32 (2008–2009) and 18 (2010–2011) patients with idiopathic uncomplicated calcium-oxylate kidney stones in the fall and winter received treatment with a herbal remedy [18,19,20]. Diuresis and fluid intake were measured by patients. In addition, the urine pH and the rate of excretion with urine, calcium, magnesium and citric acid were measured, and on the basis of these data, the ionic activity index (AP CAOX index, the risk factor of stones) and the level of crystalluria were calculated. The study documented a slight increase in diuresis. Excretion with oxalate urine (significantly), calcium (trend) and citric acid (trend) decreased, but magnesium excretion has increased (significantly) during therapy. The authors reported a significant decrease in the ionic activity index and the

frequency of crystalluria and interpreted results as a tendency to reduce lithogenesis, recommending a long course of treatment with a combination of herbs in patients with uncomplicated idiopathic calcium urolithiasis. Treatment was considered safe, adverse reactions were not reported.

Conclusion. A positive effect is established in patients with urolithiasis and after removal of stones. The use of a long course of treatment of patients with uncomplicated idiopathic calcium urolithiasis can reduce the risk of relapse of urolithiasis, as evidenced by a decrease in the ionic activity index and the frequency of crystalluria.

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